

STRING analysis in cerebellum of Pink1^{-/-} mice for KEGG pathways >1.5-fold downregulated factors, confidence 0.9, p<0.05

Age 6 weeks

Term:	p-value	n
Estrogen signaling pathway	1,41E-04	5
MAPK signaling pathway	1,66E-02	5
Cocaine addiction	2,03E-02	3
Legionellosis	3,39E-02	3
Amphetamine addiction	4,36E-02	3

Age 6 months

Term:	p-value	n
MAPK signaling pathway	1,46E-03	13
Estrogen signaling pathway	2,98E-03	8
Dopaminergic synapse	3,08E-03	9
Cocaine addiction	4,29E-03	6
FoxO signaling pathway	5,41E-03	9
TNF signaling pathway	8,24E-03	8
Protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum	2,92E-02	9

Age 18 months

Term:	p-value	n
MAPK signaling pathway	7,73E-06	36
SNARE interaction in vesicular transport	1,31E-04	11
Thyroid hormone signaling pathway	1,85E-04	21
Retrograde endocannabinoid signaling	1,30E-03	18
Ras signaling pathway	3,29E-03	28
Glycerophospholipid metabolism	3,94E-03	16
Proteoglycans in cancer	7,65E-03	27
Neurotrophin signaling pathway	9,14E-03	18
Rap1 signaling pathway	9,16E-03	26
Endocytosis	9,95E-03	26
Protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum	1,27E-02	22
Ubiquitin mediated proteolysis	1,96E-02	19
Dopaminergic synapse	2,01E-02	18
Circadian entrainment	2,34E-02	15
Renal cell carcinoma	2,69E-02	12
Platelet activation	3,38E-02	18
Phosphatidylinositol signaling system	4,89E-02	13

6 Weeks

log2 C18M

log2 C6M

log2 C6W

- PRKACB
- RPS96A5
- FOS
- HSPA1A
- HSPA1B
- MAP3K14
- MAP4K2
- CACNG4
- GRB2
- FLNC
- NFT
- FLNB
- FLNA
- PLA2G2F
- PDGFRB
- RASGRP2
- FGF11
- PLA2G4B
- FGF14
- MAPK8IP1
- STMN1
- NTF3
- HSPA8
- PAK1
- DUSP10
- RPS96A3
- MAP2K7
- MAPK1
- MAP2K4
- FGF1
- SOS1
- FGF22
- FGF9
- ELK1
- CACNG7
- MAP3K13
- MAPK8IP2
- CACNA1E
- PRKCA
- PTFN5
- TACK2
- FGF18
- SOS2
- PRKACA
- MKNK2
- MAPK8
- HSPB1
- RASA2
- MAPKAPK5
- PLA2G4A
- NFKB2
- NFATC2
- PLA2G4E
- MAP3K6
- RPS96A1
- MAP3K8
- CACNG1
- CACNA1H
- DUSP5
- DDIT3
- JUN
- CACNB4
- CACNA1D
- MAPK10
- PPP3CB
- MEF2C
- CASP3
- MKNK1
- MAP3K5
- RRAS2
- MAP3K4
- MAP3K2
- MAP3K6
- PLA2G12A
- MAPT
- CACNB1
- RASGRF2
- TGFB1
- TACK1
- RASGRP3
- RASGRF1
- EGFR
- TGFB2
- RPS96A2
- SRF
- MAP4K3
- CACNG8
- RAPGEF2
- GADD45G
- MAP2K1
- TGFB3
- GADD45A
- STK4
- TGFB2
- MAPK13
- CD14
- CACNA1A
- NTRK1
- MAPK12
- MAPK11
- IL1R1
- GADD45B
- RELB
- FGF3
- PDGFB
- CDC25B
- MAP3K3
- MAP4K4
- CACNA2D2
- CACNA1G
- RPS96A4
- MAP3K2
- FGF16
- NTRK2
- CACNG2
- MAPK7
- MAP3K1
- RELA
- MAP2K3
- KIBK
- RAF1
- CACNA1C
- HSPA2
- TGFB1
- FGF5
- CACNB3
- FGFR1
- PPP3R1
- MYC
- PPP3CA
- DUSP7
- RAC3
- NFKB1
- PPP5C
- RAP1A
- CACNA1B
- PDGFA
- NRAS
- MAPKAPK2
- DUSP3
- PTPRR
- KIBK
- MAPKAPK3
- DUSP8
- DUSP16
- NLK
- MAPK3
- CACNA2D3
- ARRB2
- TACK3
- ATF4
- CHUK
- NR4A1
- DUSP1
- GNA12
- PPM1B
- FGFR2
- PPM1A
- MAP2K5
- RAC1
- FGF12
- STK3
- CACNG3
- FGF13
- RASGRP1
- CACNB2
- MAPK9
- KRAS
- CRK
- CACNA2D1
- CRKL
- AKT3
- MAPK14
- DUSP4
- PLA2G5
- FGFR3
- PLA2G3
- BDNF
- PAK2
- PDGFR
- KIBK
- MAX
- CACNG5
- TRAF6
- FGF7
- PRKX
- MAPK8IP3
- BRAF
- RAC1
- DUSP14
- RAP1B
- AKT2
- GNG12
- DUSP8
- RPS96A6
- MAP3K7
- ATF2
- AKT1